

methyl heptenone, *d*- α -phellandrene, *d*-citronellal, linalool, citronellol, nerol, geraniol and geranyl acetate was established.

The I.R. spectra and co-TLC of the fractions also confirmed the above results. The alcohols were confirmed by the TLC of their 3,5-dinitrobenzoates over Silica Gel G coated glass plates using different solvent systems and anisaldehyde-H₂SO₄ as spray reagent. The R_F values (using butter yellow as a reference compound) in benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) were observed to be 1.6, 1.3, 1.2 corresponding to citronellol, nerol and geraniol respectively.

Fig. 1.

Chromatogram : Oil of *Cymbopogon nardus*
var : stracheyi

Conditions—

Column—10% Carbowax 20 m
Column temp.—180°C
Carrier gas—Hydrogen (40 ml/min)
Chart speed—0.25 inch/min.

Gas-liquid Chromatography : The GLC of the oil was carried out in a gas chromatograph model—Honeywell HP 7620A equipped with thermal conductivity detector and Carbowax 20M, 10% (18 ft.) column. The column and injection port temperatures were maintained at 180° and 200° respectively, and hydrogen (40 ml/min.) was used as carrier gas. The eleven peaks obtained in the chromatogram were identified by comparing their retention and relative retention times to those of the authentic samples recorded under identical operating conditions. The percentage of each constituent in the oil was determined by calculating corresponding peak area by height \times width at half height method. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Thus, the GLC revealed the presence of one more constituent, i.e., camphene in addition to those identified by chemical methods.

TABLE 1—GLC OF ESSENTIAL OIL OF *C. nardus* VAR. stracheyi

Peak No.	Retention time (minutes)	Percentage in the oil	Compound
1	1.3	0.25	camphene
2	1.5	15.0	β -pinene
3	2.0	28.0	limonene
4	2.5	16.25	α -phellandrene
5	3.0	3.0	methyl heptenone
6	4.6	5.5	citronellal
7	5.6	8.0	linalool
8	12.6	6.0	citronellol
9	12.7	7.0	geranyl acetate
10	14.8	3.0	nerol
11	16.2	8.0	geraniol

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for providing financial assistance.

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Colouring Matters from the Flowers of *Thunbergia laurifolia*

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Manuscript received 9 January 1978, revised 9 March 1978,

accepted 5 May 1978

THE plant *Thunbergia laurifolia* (N. O. Acanthaceae) is a large climber and is found throughout India¹. The flowers, light blue in colour with yellowish throat, on chemical examination yielded Delphinidin 3 : 5-di-*o*- β -D-glucopyranoside, apigenin and apigenin-7-*o*- β -D-glucopyranoside.

The fresh flowers were extracted with 1% methanolic hydrochloric acid and the extract after concentration under reduced pressure was extracted with ether. The violet red solution gave compound A and the dried ether extract on crystallisation from acetone : methanol (1 : 1) gave compound B. The extracted flowers were air-dried and refluxed with ethanol for 10 hr. The concentrated extract on crystallisation from methanol : benzene (1 : 1) gave compound C.

Compound A (*anthocyanin*) ; violet-red ; hygroscopic ; λ_{\max} 535 nm, shift in AlCl₃ (25 nm). Hydrolysis with 20% CH₃OH-HCl gave anthocyanidin and a sugar identified to be D-glucose. The antho-

cyanidin was identified to be Delphinidin by its standard R_f values², colour reactions³ and λ_{\max} 545 nm, shift in $AlCl_3$ (25 nm). Periodate oxidation and the hydrolysis with emulsin suggested the glucose molecules to be in pyranose forms and linked through β -linkages. The anthocyanin was confirmed by direct comparison with its authentic sample isolated from *Verbena hybrida*⁴.

Compound B (*flavone aglycone*); yellow solid, $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$, m.p. 346°, gave negative Molisch test; λ_{\max} 269 nm and 336 nm; R_f value 0.88 in *n*-butanol; acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5); $KMnO_4$ oxidation gave *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid and KOH fusion gave phloroglucinol indicating the presence of free hydroxyls at positions-4', 5 and 7. These positions were also shown by the colours given with $NaHCO_3$ (blue), methanolic $ZrOCl$ (yellow) and vanillin-HCl reagent (pink) and confirmed by the bathochromic shifts with $NaOC_2H_5$ (56 nm in Band I), $AlCl_3$ (9 & 46 nm) and fused $NaOAc$ (9 & 40 nm). Hence, the compound B was identified to be a 4', 5 : 7 trihydroxy flavone, i.e., apigenin.

Compound C (*flavone glycoside*); yellow crystals; $C_{21}H_{20}O_{10}$; m.p., 174°; gave positive Molisch test showing its glycosidic nature; λ_{\max} 268 nm and 335 nm. Hydrolysis with 10% H_2SO_4 gave an aglycone identical to the compound B and a sugar identified to be D-glucose. Oxidation with $KMnO_4$ gave *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid. The negative colour test with vanillin-HCl reagent and no shift in Band II with fused $NaOAc$ indicated the position-7 to be glycosylated.

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Flavonoids from Flowers of *Hamellia patensa*

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Manuscript received 21 January 1978, accepted 5 May 1978

HAMELLIA *patensa* (N.O. Rubiaceae) is a shrub of immense medicinal use, Presence of two anthocyanins viz. Petunidine 3,5-diglucoside and Malvidine 3,5-diglucoside have already been reported from the fresh flowers¹. In the present communication the authors wish to report the flavonoid constituents of the flowers of *H. patensa*.

The air dried flowers (about 2 Kg.) of *H. patensa* were extracted with acetone under reflux on

a steam bath. The acetone extract was concentrated to a syrupy mass and was poured in large excess of water. The water soluble and water insoluble fractions were separated. The water soluble fraction was concentrated and successively subjected to sexhelet extraction with petroleum ether, benzene and ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate fraction was concentrated and then adsorbed over a column of magnesol. Elution with ethyl acetate yielded two substances A and B. Both these substances gave positive Molisch's test. The purity of the substances was checked by P.C. and T.L.C.

The compound A crystallised from acetone M.P. 340-2° (d) $C_{21}H_{18}O_{11}$ when being hydrolysed yielded an aglycone M.P. 349-50° $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ which gave positive colour reactions (e.g., Mg/HCl) for flavonoids and was found to be identical with apigenin (M.P. U.V. shift, Co. chromatography, m.m.p. and super imposable I.R. spectra with authentic sample), and glucuronic acid as Sugar moiety (identified by paper chromatography with authentic sample). Compound A was thus characterised as Apigenin-7-glucuronide².

The compound B Crystallised from Methanol M.P. 188° $C_{27}H_{30}O_{16}$. On acid hydrolysis yielded an aglycone M.P. 316°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_7$ identical with quercetin (by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with authentic sample) and sugars D(+) glucose and L(-) rhamnose (identified by paper chromatography with authentic sample). Hence compound B was identified as rutin³ by m.m.p. chromatography and super imposable I.R. spectra with authentic sample.

The water insoluble fraction of the acetone extract was chromatographed on a column of magnesol which was eluted with ethyl acetate. The eluate yielded compound C which responded positive test for flavones. It was recrystallised from acetone-methanol (3 : 1 V/V) m.p. 348-50° $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$. It did not respond to Molisch's test. It was identified as apigenin by m.m.p., super imposable I.R. and co-chromatography with authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.D.T.) is obliged to U.G.C. for the award of teacher fellowship.

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